

DEVELOPING TOURIST DESTINATION POTENTIAL UNDER INFLUENCE OF INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL FACTORS

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Abstract

This paper aims to identify the main factors of attractiveness of a leisure tourist destination that have the greatest impact on the tourism potential of the area. To this end, a theoretical review was conducted based on the topics of management and planning of tourist destinations, in general, and the conditioning factors of attractiveness of tourist destinations, in particular. Based on the analysis of the academic literature, the authors identified internal and external factors that affect the attractiveness of the tourist destination. The empirical study was conducted as a case study in Russia, with application of an online survey by e-mail to experts in planning and management of tourist destinations, in order to collect their perceptions about the importance of the factors of attractiveness of a tourist destination and highlighted their parameters, collate them with the pre-existing literature and consolidate a matrix of relevant categories for the analysis of the topic. The results explore the internal and external factors that affect the functioning of the attractiveness of the tourist destination. While the former focus directly on the destination's operations and functionality, allowing to improve the tourism potential in a given period of time; the external factors are the source of consumer provision on a legislative basis and take into account national and international developments. It was concluded that the attractiveness of the tourist destination, responsible for the tourism potential of the territory, lies in the balanced interaction of internal and external factors.

Keywords: Tourism gnoseology; Tourist destination; Tourism potential of the area; External factors; Internal factors.

DESENVOLVIMENTO DO POTENCIAL DE DESTINO TURÍSTICO SOB INFLUÊNCIA DE FATORES INTERNOS E EXTERNOS**Resumo**

O objetivo deste artigo é identificar quais são os principais fatores de atratividade de um destino turístico de lazer que têm maior impacto no potencial turístico da área. Para tanto, realizou-se uma revisão teórica baseada nos temas de gestão e planejamento de destinos turísticos, em geral, e nos fatores condicionantes de atratividade de destinos turísticos, em particular. Com base na análise da literatura acadêmica, os autores identificaram fatores internos e externos que afetam a atratividade do destino turístico. O estudo empírico se deu sob a forma de um estudo de caso na Rússia, com aplicação de um *survey* online por e-mail junto a especialistas em planejamento e gestão de destinos turísticos, a fim de coletar suas percepções a importância dos fatores de atratividade de um destino turístico e destacaram seus parâmetros, cotejando-as com a literatura pré-existente e consolidar uma matriz de categorias relevantes para a análise do tema. Os resultados exploram os fatores internos e externos que afetam o funcionamento da atratividade do destino turístico. Enquanto os primeiros incidem diretamente sobre as operações do destino e sua funcionalidade, permitindo melhorar o potencial turístico em um determinado período de tempo; os fatores externos são a fonte da provisão do consumidor em uma base legislativa e levam em conta os desenvolvimentos nacionais e internacionais. Concluiu-se que a atratividade do destino turístico, responsável pelo potencial turístico do território, jaz na interação balanceada de fatores internos e externos.

Palavras-chave: Gnoseologia do turismo; Destino turístico; Potencial turístico da área; Fatores externos; Fatores internos.

DESARROLLO DEL POTENCIAL DE DESTINO TURÍSTICO BAJO LA INFLUENCIA DE FACTORES INTERNOS Y EXTERNOS**Resumen**

El objetivo de este artículo es identificar cuáles son los principales factores de atractividad de un destino turístico de ocio que tienen mayor impacto sobre el potencial turístico de la zona. Para ello, se realizó una revisión teórica basada en los temas de gestión y planificación de destinos turísticos, en general, y los condicionantes del atractivo de los destinos turísticos, en particular. A partir del análisis de la literatura académica, los autores identificaron los factores internos y externos que afectan al atractivo del destino turístico. El estudio empírico se llevó a cabo en forma de estudio de caso en Rusia, con aplicación de una encuesta online por correo electrónico a expertos en planificación y gestión de destinos turísticos, con el fin de recoger sus percepciones sobre la importancia de los factores de atractivo de un destino turístico y destacar sus parámetros, cotejarlos con la literatura preexistente y consolidar una matriz de categorías relevantes para el análisis del tema. Los resultados exploran los factores internos y externos que afectan al funcionamiento del atractivo del destino turístico. Mientras que los primeros se centran directamente en las operaciones y la funcionalidad del destino, lo que permite mejorar el potencial turístico en un periodo de tiempo determinado; los factores externos son la fuente de provisión de los consumidores sobre una base legislativa y tienen en cuenta la evolución nacional e internacional. Se llegó a la conclusión de que el atractivo del destino turístico, responsable del potencial turístico del territorio, reside en la interacción equilibrada de los factores internos y externos.

Palabras clave: Gnoseología turística; Destino turístico; Potencial turístico de la zona; Factores externos; Factores internos.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the modern context, tourism is a complex phenomenon of public life, an extensive social system that is becoming an important factor in the formation of a modern way of using the free time of the population by society and

meeting the needs of a modern person (Mosalev et al., 2018). The present is characterized by significant transformations in lifestyle and its social, political, economic foundations, etc. (Kryukova et al., 2018a). These transformations are global as they are transformations of cultural paradigms. It is now that an unregulated cultural space is emerging. Therefore,

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tourism in the modern context requires academic reflection, and its various theoretical and practical aspects have already been comprehended, one of which is the attractiveness of Tourist Destinations (TD) (Kryukova et al., 2018b).

One of the most important – if not the most – activities in the tourism sector lays on what makes a particular area become interesting or “attractive” to tourists. Thus, the first step in the current study of tourism is to determine the epistemological aspects of tourism in its overall transformation, or what makes an area become popular. Tourist destination attractiveness (TDA) plays an extremely important role in the development of the tourist potential of the territory (Kryukova et al., 2021).

The noticeable growth of tourism in recent decades is due, first of all, to the emergence of new technical capabilities, in the development of factors that form the basis of the attractiveness of a TD (Bondarenko et al., 2020). This is supported by the idea that in the current information age, material goods that dominated the goals of post-industrial society are being replaced by spiritual values, such as experiences and sensations, which are the main purpose of tourist trips (Haugland et al., 2011).

However, along with certain factors, we consider it necessary to focus on the fact that the demand for health improvement, recreation, positive experiences largely depends on the quality of the TD, which helps to ensure a high level in the provision of these services. This level can be achieved through a consistent and structured study and description of heterogeneous factors of the attractiveness of a TD and identifying the most optimal factors, both internal, inherent exclusively in this destination, and external, having a direct or indirect impact on the destination.

In Russia, due to the recent process of modernization, such issues are still underdeveloped and needs to be deepened in order to generate more solutions to expand and explore the Russian potential in tourism sector. Thus, in this context, the research question that drives this study is: what are the main factors of attractiveness of a leisure tourist destination that have the greatest impact on the tourism potential of the area?

To answer it, this paper aims to identify that factors in a double way, firstly making a scientific literature review on the topic and secondly, through a case study with Russian researchers, in order to collect their perceptions about the importance of the factors of attractiveness of a TD and highlighted their parameters, collate them with the pre-existing literature and consolidate a matrix of relevant categories for the analysis of the topic.

The main contribution of the paper is to create a consolidate matrix with the main relevant categories related to the factors of attractiveness of a TD. This has theoretical and practical implications. The former are related to the consolidation of the existing information and the possibility to create a necessary check point in order to go further with the theoretical exploration of the issue. The later (practical) implications are related to the possibility to use that matrix as a guide to implement tourist projects, programs and plans in a TD. After all, considering the Russian context, this kind of study is helpful in order to update the general conditions of exploration the tourism issue, be on the theoretical and academic sense or in the practical and economic one.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Systems Theory is the most used framework to study and guide practical applications on tourism. According to Hall (2008) the planning process is central and strategic in the tourist systems whatever be the scale considered.

The management of tourist system, based on the systems theory approach, can be understood as a set of 3 macro process: inputs, through puts and outputs, where the through puts is the central one in the terms of processing activities necessary to make the tourism activity happen.

Figure 1. Opening the black box of tourism planning and policy systems.

Source: Hall (2008: 15).

The division of the environment and the system makes a separation of the activities performed inside and outside the tourist system. Andriots (2000) considers three types of environment affecting the tourism system, either directly or indirectly. The first *internal environment* which includes policy, planning, marketing, organisational, financial, and human variables; the second one is the *operating environment* which includes the tourists (domestic and foreign), the suppliers of the input (capital, labour, land, technology, materials, power etc.), the competition from other industries (e.g. leisure) and the competition from other destinations; and finally the third one is the *macro-environment*, which deals with the macro societal – social, cultural, economic, legal, natural, etc. – variables.

Figure 2. The three environments of the tourism system.

Source: reproduced from Liu (1994: 21) and Andriots (2000: 68).

While planning is a 'many sided phenomenon' (Tosun & Jenkins, 1998), the system approach supports that successful tourism planning is essential to incorporate socio-cultural, economic, political, technological and geographical variables, because these extra / outside variables can also have impact on what happens inside the system.

In Latin America, Brazilian researchers also have dedicated attention to the topic. De Oliveira Santos (2007) has classified 2 main approaches on tourism destinations management and planning: one focused on spatial models – such as from Marriot & Pearce (2003), Palhares (2002), Leiper (2002), among others – and the other one based on

models oriented by systems theory [for example: Inskip (2001), Moscardo (2001) and Hall (2001) and Beni (1998)].

Whatever will be the case, it is clear that there is a direct interplay between the spatial and the socioeconomic (or productive) categories. And for the productive purposes, inside the management and planning system of a TD (seen as a tourism system), one of the most important elements is the attractiveness. As for the subject of the study – tourist destination attractiveness as a component of the tourist potential of the territory – scholars use a wide range of different definitions (Table 1).

Table 1. Generalization and systematization of the definition of "tourist destination attractiveness" (TDA).

Authors	Definition
Deng, King, Bauer, 2002	is a dynamic characteristic of a tourist destination, with the help of which the possibility of expanding tourism activities in different directions is acquired
Kim, Perdue, 2011	a tourist-attractive destination is a destination that is popular with tourists and this area turns into a tourist center
Cracolici, Nijkamp, 2008	the presence of such a tourist potential of the territory, the operation of which ensures the optimal tourist load and the full preservation of tourist resources, and the possibility of obtaining a socio-economic effect without violating the environmental balance
Reitsamer et al., 2016	tourist attractiveness is often inconsistent and can change depending on many factors that affect the attractiveness of a tourist destination. These include the availability of a modern material and technical base of tourism, in particular, the latest hotel complexes, specialized establishments with an appropriate range of services that they provide, etc.

Source: own elaboration.

At the same time, the tourist potential of a territory is defined as a set of possibilities of natural resources, historical and cultural complexes, objects, and socio-economic indicators in a certain territory, which allows one to create conditions for organized tourism, recreation, and other types of recreational activities in compliance with its protection (Formica, Uysal, 2006), which, in our opinion, can "work" subject to the existing attractiveness of the TD. This wording implies linking into a single whole, into a single system of various factors of a TDA, which is a rather difficult task.

The present of tourism is characterized by a rather wide diversity in the formation of the thesaurus and a variety of approaches to determining the factors of tourism development (Hsu et al., 2010). Modern tourism researchers (Ul Islam, Chaudhary, 2021) have identified internal and external factors that affect tourism in various ways.

The external factors are related to the demographic and social changes; economic and financial development; changes in political and legal regulation; technological changes; development of transport infrastructure; travel safety (Quadri-Felitti, Fiore, 2013).

By their turn, the internal factors are related to the productive system, being essentially market factors, such as: processes of demand and supply; segmentation of the market in which the tourist product develops; proper marketing; private sector of tourism; human factor (Cho, 2008).

At the same time, internal factors are a set of components interconnected through certain structures within a certain place. The main variables are geographic location, information, resources (natural and anthropogenic), infrastructure, and personnel that ensure the efficiency of TDA.

Internal variables shall be called sociotechnical subsystems because such variables have a social component (people) and a technical component (other internal variables) (Cho, 2008).

External factors are a set of elements that have a certain influence on each of the internal factors in their close interaction: with direct impact – legislation, domestic events, and with indirect impact – the state of the economy, international events, political and socio-cultural factors (Quadri-Felitti, Fiore, 2013).

At the same time, the opinion (Kozak et al., 2005) on the factors of the location of tourist enterprises is notable. The most important of the factors is tourist demand, which determines the concentration of recreation facilities in the main areas of settlement.

The next factor is the availability of tourism resources, their quantity, quality, variety, combination, and availability. The third factor is the availability of the labor force. The fourth is the infrastructural readiness of the TD (the level of development of transport, public utilities). The fifth factor is the remoteness of places of rest from places of residence, which determines the cost of travel and travel time.

In a more specific way, Carvalho & Pimentel (2014) have dedicated attention to the conditioning factors of planning and management in TD. The authors have systematized and classified the existing literature into 6 main areas – physical factors, economic factors, organizational factors, sociocultural factors, institutional factors and random factors— each one of them having both sides, one internal to the TD and the other external being related to the external environment in which a tourism destination is inserted in. Table 2 shows the synthesis of the conditioning factors of planning in TD, according to Carvalho & Pimentel (2014).

Table 2. Synthesis of the conditioning factors of planning in Tourist Destinations.

Physical factors		Economic factors		Organizational factors	
External physical factors	Internal physical factors	External economic factors	Internal economic factors	External organizational factors	Internal organizational factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Geographical Aspects (relief features; climate; etc.) ■ Spatial location (distance from an emissive tourist center; distance from another competing receptive center). ■ Infrastructure of the environment (availability/ conditions of access roads; etc.); ■ Transport system that connects emitters and receivers (modals available and their conditions, frequency / comfort / attractiveness / regularity of services); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ (basic) infrastructure of the system (availability and conditions of public roads, traffic signs; traffic jams; public and private transportation services; water and electricity supply, sewage collection, public lighting and garbage collection; security, police stations and fire departments; medical care capacity, etc.); ■ Tourist infrastructure (tourist equipment and services; tourist signage; tourist information center; tourist service center, tourist protection service, etc.); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Tourist income; ■ Financing /Financing of travel; ■ Financial stability; ■ Substitute effects of the offer; ■ Offer price index; ■ Diversification of supply; ■ Exchange rates. ■ Way of marketing consolidators and emissive tourism agencies; ■ Financing concessions to companies in the sector; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Local economy ■ GDP of the municipality; ■ Tax collection. ■ Entrepreneurs hip; ■ Financing for local enterprises; ■ Production costs; ■ Forms of commercialization of TD in distributors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Bodies or entities, public or private, national, regional or local studies and research (availability of statistical data, demand research, monitoring and evaluation of activity, etc.) ■ Research, innovation and technology centers in tourism ■ Relationship with other tourist centers (competition or complementarity/ partnership); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Number and diversity of tourist organizations (from different sectors: food, lodging, attractions, etc.; and forms: public, private, non-state public); ■ Organizational networks (interactions, agreements and institutionalization of actions among DT actors). ■ Management organization of the tourist destination (existence of executing entity, management of DT production, promotion and distribution of TD, internal communication; administrative capacity; technology and innovation, etc.);
Sociocultural factors		Institutional factors		Random factors	
External sociocultural factors	Internal sociocultural factors	External institutional factors	Internal institutional factors	External organizational factors	Internal organizational factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Free time; ■ Influence of social groups; ■ Motivation of the trip; ■ Personal characteristics; ■ Demographic aspects (age; sex; religion, marital status; profession; qualification; etc.); ■ Level of income and schooling; ■ Quality of life; ■ Previous experiences. ■ Image of the place; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Demographic aspects of the residents of the destination; ■ Level of income and schooling of residents of the destinations; ■ Offer of jobs to dt residents; ■ Community participation in tourism; ■ Local culture (preservation of heritage; sense of territorial identity, etc.); ■ Commercialized image of DT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Environmental legislation; U. Conservation; ■ Tourism policy; ■ Indicators for the evaluation of plans/projects; ■ Monitoring the implementation of policies; ■ ABNT Standards (events, companies, public areas); ■ Environmental disaster prevention and contingency plan; ■ Public policies other than 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Municipal tourist planning; ■ Environmental legislation; ■ Supervision and standardization of the operation of tourist services; ■ Planning for crisis and disaster management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Armed conflicts; ■ Terrorism; ■ Pandemias/epidemics; ■ Climate disasters; ■ Technological failures; ■ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ They were not identified in the internal scope according to the scope attributed to this sphere of tourist planning in this study.

Source: reproduced from Carvalho & Pimentel (2014:184).

However, in various literary sources, there is no clear system of attractiveness factors for a TD, the methods for identifying them within each region (place, center) require thoroughness in the application.

According to researchers (Krešić, Prebežac, 2011), the creation of an efficient system of TDA factors requires a comprehensive study of their characteristics using specific methods. Only a few studies (Lim et al., 2016; Kryukova et

al., 2018b) are related to determining the influence of TDA factors on the efficiency of using its tourist potential. Therefore, assessing the degree of influence of certain factors on the efficiency of the functioning of tourism is a promising task.

Thus, this paper aims to analyze the attractiveness factors of the recreational TD as a component of the tourist potential of the area. To achieve this goal, one must solve the

following tasks: a) determine the functional composition of the attractiveness factors of the recreational TD in Russia; and, b) to determine the significance of the attractiveness factors of the recreational tourist destination in Russia.

It is assumed as a research hypothesis that the TDA of recreational tourism in Russia, as a component of the tourist potential of the territory, is the interaction of internal factors that are the source of the functioning of TDA, make it possible to improve the tourist potential in a certain period, and external factors that are the source of providing consumers with legislative basis and taking into account domestic and international developments.

3 METHODS

The methodological framework of the study includes both theoretical (analysis of scientific literature) and empirical research methods. To determine the level of TDA one must have an idea of both internal and external factors, their potential, and development trends. Based on the analysis of the literature (e.g. Kozak et al. (2005); Formic & Uysal (2006); Cho (2008); Hsu et al. (2010); Quadri-Felitti & Fiore (2013); Carvalho & Pimentel (2014); Ul Islam, Chaudhary (2021) among others), we identified internal and external factors that affect the TDA for recreational tourism in Russia.

To determine the significance of the attractiveness factors of recreational TD in Russia, the method of an online survey by e-mail was used. The questions, according to the objectives of the study, were aimed at determining the experts' opinions on attractiveness factors of the TD of recreational tourism in Russia.

The study was conducted from November to December 2021. The empirical study was conducted with a sample of 78 experts specializing in the tourism industry in Russia. Of these experts, 38 worked in travel companies, while the remaining 40 were employed in other niches of the tourism services sector, including hotels, resorts, and other tourism-related businesses.

The experts were chosen based on their professional experience and expertise in the tourism industry, and

represented a diverse range of backgrounds and regions within the target destinations.

The experts came from a variety of locations, including urban and rural areas, and had experience working in a variety of tourism-related fields, such as marketing, hospitality, and event planning. Many of the experts had extensive experience in their respective fields and had developed a deep understanding of the challenges and opportunities facing the tourism industry.

The experts' opinions on various attractiveness factors of a TD of recreational tourism in Russia were assigned a rank on a scale from one (the least important factor) to five (the most significant factor). Based on a likert scale.

Moreover, according to the results of the online survey, to increase the reliability of the findings, a correlation analysis of the obtained data was carried out using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. The descriptive statistics was used to show the profile of the sample.

4 RESULTS

The internal and external factors (obtained based on the analysis of scientific literature) that affect the attractiveness of the Russian TD of recreational tourism are presented in Table 2).

Table 2. Factors of tourist destination attractiveness.

Internal Factors	External Factors with direct influence	External Factors with indirect influence
geographic location	legislation	the state of the economy
resources	domestic developments	international developments
infrastructure		geopolitical and sociocultural factors
information		
human resources		

Source: own elaboration.

Expert assessment of attractiveness factors of a tourist destination for recreational tourism is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Expert assessment of attractiveness factors of a tourist destination.

Attractiveness factors	Total sample, N = 78	Business area	
		Travel agency N = 38	Tourist services N = 40
Internal:			
geographic location	4.33	4.51	4.18
resources	3.26	2.86	3.68
infrastructure	3.66	4.15	3.15
information	3.42	3.83	3.12
human resources	3.14	2.78	3.24
External, direct influence:			
legislation	2.33	2.48	2.23
domestic developments	1.32	1.23	1.42
External, indirect influence			
state of the economy	3.79	4.18	3.52
international developments	2.57	2.75	2.48
geopolitical and sociocultural factors	2.21	2.26	2.14

Source: own elaboration.

Analyzing the results presented in Table 2, one can conclude that the most significant internal factors of tourist destination attractiveness in Russia are the geographical

location (4.33) and the existing infrastructure (3.66). On the other hand, the least important internal factor, according to respondents, is "human resources" (3.14).

The results of the correlation analysis showed that there is a close relationship between such *internal factors* of destination attractiveness as "existing infrastructure" and "resources" ($r_s = 0.422$), "geographic location" and "information" ($r_s = 0.534$).

Analyzing the significance of *external factors* of tourist destination attractiveness, one can conclude that the most significant external factor is the state of the economy (3.79), and the least important is "internal developments" (3.14).

Furthermore, the results of the correlation analysis showed that there is a close relationship between such external factors of the destination attractiveness as "the state of the economy" and "legislation" ($r_s = 0.416$).

4 DISCUSSION

Table 2 contains a generalization of heterogeneous factors of tourist destination attractiveness, which will help determine the degree of their influence on the demand for tourism potential in various territories.

The study of the internal and external factors of tourist destination attractiveness identified by us, qualitative assessment, selection of priorities for the relevant indicators lead to the solution of the multi-criteria problem of optimizing the tourism potential, which makes it possible to reduce the negative impact of various elements, as well as increase the possibility of boosting the demand for the tourism product.

We believe that geographical location as an internal factor plays one of the key roles in the development of tourism potential (Carvalho & Pimentel, 2014). From this perspective, the most significant is the transport and geographic location of the tourist destination. In tourism, its profitability allows for the spatial interaction of various elements of the territorial transport system. Indeed, for each tourist, the accessibility of the destination, the connectivity, and the permeability of the tourist destination are important (Cracolici, Nijkamp, 2008).

The role of information about the tourist destination attractiveness today is quite significant. Researchers (Quadri-Felitti, Fiore, 2013) believe that the number of tourists who want to visit the area largely depends on the amount of available information about tourist destinations. A developed information complex implies the availability of sufficient and accessible information about the tourism potential, the tourist destination attractiveness (mass media information, tourist Internet communications, printed materials), and tourism activities within it (Kim, Perdue, 2011).

As for resources, let us note that one may use natural resources (beaches, water areas, mountains, etc.), cultural and historical resources (historical sites of the city, museums, theaters), recreational resources (national parks, nature reserves, resorts, etc.), major cultural events (carnivals in Latin America, sports events, art festivals, annual exhibitions, etc.), specific interest (shopping, casinos, etc.). According to researchers (Hsu et al., 2010), the main resources that represent the internal factors of tourist destination attractiveness, in addition to natural ones, are cultural-historical, recreational-tourist, socio-economic, socio-demographic, and economic resources, which can be combined into anthropogenic tourism resources as the driving force behind their emergence is people.

The infrastructure factor is a set of facilities, institutions, structures, networks, and other elements of the material and technical framework that make it possible to carry out tourism activities. The "infrastructure" factor, according to researchers (Kozak, Bigné, Andreu, 2005), also includes industries that produce goods and services for tourism; temporary accommodation establishments, the catering industry (for example, restaurant facilities), the entertainment industry, passenger transportation, banking, and insurance services, etc.

The human resources factor, which contributes to the development of the attractiveness of a tourist destination, is formally divided (Formica, Uysal, 2006) into "service staff" and "management bodies".

Despite the importance of the quality of staff in the tourism industry, postulated in various foreign studies (Reitsamer et al., 2016; Cho, 2008), in this study, this factor is the least important compared to other internal factors of tourist destination attractiveness in Russia, such as "geographical location", "existing infrastructure", "resources", and "information". This might be due to the psychological traits of our compatriots, on the one hand, showing great independence in organizing their recreation, on the other hand, accustomed to the low quality of service from tourism staff.

The effect of legislation as an external factor of direct influence lies in the fact that compliance with the legislative framework in tourism policy within the framework of the country's political, economic, and social potential is the main vector of the state's socio-economic policy, which regulates and coordinates the development of the tourism industry through a variety of methods.

At the same time, the external factor of indirect influence "the state of the economy" provides for the involvement of both material and spiritual production in the tourism industry, the involvement of several related industries into the orbit of its influence. At the same time, the uniqueness of the tourism product determines the extremely complicated and complex nature of the impact of tourism on the national economy and increases the responsibility of states for the efficiency of tourism (Hsu et al., 2010).

The "international developments" factor, according to researchers (Deng, King, Bauer, 2002), is quite significant, since many countries of the world regulate the sphere of foreign tourism at a certain legislative level. This requires international cooperation both on a global and regional basis through direct international cooperation and through the channels of international organizations such as the World Trade Organization (WTO), as well as between various components of the private tourism sector through non-governmental and professional organizations.

Speaking about geopolitical and sociocultural factors, researchers (Krešić, Prebežac, 2011) note that in order to understand the features of the influence of the geopolitical factor on annual tourist flows, it is important to take into account from the very beginning that this is the most dynamic and socio-culturally loaded part of travel (Carvalho & Pimentel, 2014). Tourist movements change the socio-cultural orientation of the tourist, but these movements are far from accidental and are always associated with clearly defined features and stages of development of a tourist destination.

The need for the socio-cultural development of society through tourism has been proven by many researchers (Ul Islam, Chaudhary, 2021; Cho, 2008), since a person, as a responsible member of society, should aim at, first of all, an active study of the environment.

All in all, it can be concluded that for each tourist destination and a certain time period in which its tourism potential will be used, there will be a composition of attractive components according to prevailing factors that are not sustainable.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of the article is to analyze the attractiveness factors of the recreational TD as a component of the tourist potential of the area. To achieve this goal, we have identified the functional composition of the attractiveness factors of the recreational TD in Russia and submitted them to the experts evaluation, in order to determine the significance of the attractiveness factors of the recreational tourist destination in Russia.

From the standpoint of a systemic approach, it has been determined that tourist destination attractiveness is the interaction of internal and external factors – geographic location, information, resources (natural and anthropogenic), infrastructure and human resources, laws, consumers of services (tourists), domestic developments, the state of the economy, international developments, political, and sociocultural factors. Internal factors are the source of the functioning of tourist destination attractiveness and make it possible to improve the tourism potential in a certain period of time. External factors are a source of providing consumers with a legislative basis and taking into account domestic and international developments.

The generalization of heterogeneous factors of tourist destination attractiveness made it possible to identify their parameters and requires further research. The proposed generalization of internal and external factors of tourist destination attractiveness and the established structural hierarchy promoted the identification of issues for further study. One example would be the definition of conditions for assessing heterogeneous factors, taking into account their heterogeneity and dynamic instability. Besides, a more complete and integrated solution of problems is possible through a clear definition of a methodology for assessing the influence of heterogeneous factors on the attractiveness of a tourist destination.

The limitations of the study include focusing on one (recreational) type of tourism, as well as on one country (Russia), which in modern conditions, in our opinion, is quite justified. The study was based on the opinion of experts, which tend to be more accurate, however they are still perceptions of the interviewed experts, which doesn't mean that that perceptions correspond to the reality itself. Thus, this is also one important restriction of the current study, to take into consideration, as well as the fact the sample is short and not representative from the population, being the results valid just for the case presented above, as well as to included other perspectives and viewpoints from different stakeholders in order to make a triangulation process and in this way decrease the possible bias of a narrower sample.

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Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5	A.6
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+	+	+	+	+
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+	+	+	+	+	+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+	+	+	+	+	+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+	+	+	+	+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+	+	+	+	+	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+	+	+	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	+	+	+	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	+	+	+	+	+	+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+	+	+	+	+	+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	+	+	+	+	+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+	+	+	+	+	+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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